

POLY(LACTIC ACID) BASED SINGLE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

This research was aimed to prepare the poly(lactic acid)(PLA), based single composites. The plasticized PLA matrix has been reinforced with Ingeo™ PLA fibres. Effects of processing temperature, fibre content and size on the mechanical properties and morphology of the composites were investigated. The composite was processed using a cast-film extrusion technique.

Keywords: Poly(lactic acid), Green composite, Processing, Mechanical property, Inter-phase

INTRODUCTION

Poly(lactic acid)(PLA) is one of the most attractive thermoplastic materials being developed. PLA is derived from natural resources as well as being biodegradable so it is attractive for biocomposite applications. An increase in attention in sustainable bio-composites has been driven by the potential for drop of petrochemical feedstock [1,2]. Partial-bio-composites i.e. polyolefin-cellulose are not sufficiently eco-friendly because of their petroleum-based and non-biodegradable matrix. A good interfacial adhesion between fibre and matrix is required for composites [3]. This requires compatibility between both materials, so the composites prepared from fibre and matrix of similar chemical structure are of increasing interest. Using the same component but with different physical properties for composite production such as all-PP, all-PE, all-cellulose fibre-matrix composites has been reported [4-7]. This pathway leads to the improvement of interfacial adhesion without surface modification. An all-PLA composite will reinforce the matrix PLA due to the orientation of crystals and hence enhanced tensile strength in PLA fibres. The aim of this research is to produce a fully biodegradable green composite from renewable resources using PLA for the matrix and dispersed phases. Since the melting temperatures of fibre and matrix are too close, addition of plasticizer and varying processing condition have been conducted and studied.

Figure 1 Chemical structure of poly(lactic acid).

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Poly(lactic acid) 4042D and Ingeo™ PLA fibres were obtained from Nature Work. The fibres were cut in an IKA MF10 cutting mill and sieved to provide a size range between 0.25 and 3.00 mm. Triethyl O-acetyl citrate (Mw 318.3 g/mol) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich.

Figure 2 Chemical structure of Triethyl O-acetyl citrate.

Composite Preparation

Twin-screw extruder (Prism TSC16 TC) was used for compounding plasticized PLA and cast film extruder (Lab tech 25-30/C) was used for fabricating PLA single composite sheets. Temperature setting of the cast film extruder is shown in Table 1. Effects of processing temperatures (153, 163 and 173 °C), fibre contents (1.0, 3.0 and 5.0 % wt/wt) and sizes (0.25, 1.0 and 3.0 mm) on mechanical properties and morphology of the composite have been studied. Details are presented in Table 2.

Table 1 Temperature setting of cast film extruder.

Condition	Temperature (°C)				
	T-die and Connector	Zone 4	Zone 3	Zone 2	Zone 1 (Feed)
1	153	153	148	148	148
2	163	163	153	143	133
3	173	173	163	153	133

Table 2 Set of various conditions for composite processing.

Studied parameter	Maximum processing temperature	Fibre-sieved size (mm)	Fibre content (% wt/wt)
1. Temperature effect	153, 163, 173	1.0	5.0
2. Fibre content	153	1.0	1.0, 3.0, 5.0
3. Fibre size	163	0.25, 1.0, 3.0	3.0

Characterisation

Thermal Analysis

Differential scanning calorimetry was performed using a TA instruments DSC 2910. Temperature programs for the tests were from 30-240 °C at a heating rate of 20 °C/min. The measurements were conducted under nitrogen (100 mL/min)

Microstructure and Surface Morphology

Scanning electron microscope (SEM, JEOL JSM-6480LV) was used to observe microstructure and surface morphology of the composite and PLA fibres. The specimens were coated with gold to provide a 200 Å thick-gold layer using a vacuum sputter coater.

Mechanical Properties

Mechanical properties of the PLA fibre and composites were determined by tensile testing. Gauge length was set at 25 mm. The tests were carried out on a Universal test instrument (Hounsfield, H5K-T) at speeds of 0.25 and 2.5 mm/min. for the PLA fibre and the composites, respectively. Cross section area of the fibre and the composite specimens was determined using an optical microscope and micrometer, respectively. An average value was taken from at least 10 specimens of each composite.

Wide Angle X-ray Diffraction

The PLA fibres (70 mg) annealed at different temperatures (153, 163 and 173 °C) were cut and pressed into disc using a cylindrical steel mold (diameter = 1.3 cm) with an applied pressure of about 5000 kg/cm². Fe-filtered CoK α radiation ($\lambda = 0.1790$ nm) was generated at 40 kV and 35 mA using a PHILIPS X'pert. The X-ray diffractograms were recorded from 5 to 40° of 2θ (Bragg angle) by a goniometer equipped with scintillation counter at a scanning speed of 0.02°/s and sampling rate of 2 data/s.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Plasticized PLA Matrix: Thermal and Mechanical Properties

Declining of melting temperature of the PLA matrix (Fig. 3) by an addition of citrate plasticizer content was found.

Figure 3. Melting and glass transition temperatures of plasticized PLA.

The PLA fibre and the plasticized PLA matrix show in Fig. 4 exhibits wider difference of T_m than the PLA fibre and the unplasticized PLA cast film does. This observation leads to a possibility for processing similar polymers.

Figure 4. DSC thermograms of Ingeo fibre, 10 % wt/wt TEC plasticized PLA and unplasticized PLA cast film.

Generally an improvement in flexibility of cast film can be seen when plasticizer is incorporated. However tensile stress of the plasticized PLA films decreases upon the addition of triethyl O-acetyl citrate (Fig. 5). PLA film containing 10 % wt/wt TEC shows a continual extensive drop of the mechanical properties, implying the optimum plasticizer content. Therefore this composition was chosen to be matrix for the reinforcement with IngeoTM fibre.

Figure 5. Mechanical properties of plasticized PLA.

Mechanical Properties of PLA Composite

The influence of processing temperature on the mechanical properties of composites, containing 5%wt of 1 mm sieved Ingeo™ fibre, was investigated and shown in Fig. 6. It was found that the tensile stress of the composite decreases with an increase in processing temperature. This may originate from a dramatic change of fibre shape and crystalline destruction, which will be discussed in the next sections.

Figure 6. Mechanical properties of PLA composites prepared at different processing temperatures.

The processing temperature at 153 °C was chosen to study the influence of PLA fibre content (1, 3 and 5 % wt/wt) on mechanical properties of the composites. As shown in Fig. 7, the composite containing the lowest fibre content (1%) exhibited a highest improvement of the mechanical properties especially the stress at break. No significant difference of the mechanical properties is observed even the fibre content is increased up to 5 % wt/wt. Although the temperature of processing at 153 °C was lower than the melting temperature of the PLA fibre (163 °C) and the crystalline structure of PLA fibre was preserved, poor interphase adhesion seemed to be an important factor retarding reinforcement function of the fibre.

Therefore the influence of fibre size on the mechanical properties of the composites was conducted using a slightly higher processing temperature, 163°C. This aimed to obtain a better interphase adhesion. Nevertheless the selected temperature must be low enough to (partially) maintain the crystalline structure of the reinforcing fibre. It was obvious that the composite processed at 163 °C showed the better mechanical properties than that processed at 153 °C, even lower content was incorporated.

The 1.0 mm fibre length provides the highest tensile strength at break compared to the other sizes of 0.25 and 3.0 mm (Fig 8). The orientation of long fibre size (3.0 mm) was thought to be a crucial role in the obtained property. The greater standard deviation was found in the tensile test, indicating a variation of fibre orientation.

Figure 7. Mechanical properties of PLA composites that was prepared at different fibre contents.

Figure 8. Mechanical properties of PLA composites that was prepared at different fibre sizes.

Morphology of PLA Single Composites

The PLA compound contained 10 % wt/wt citrate plasticizer was chosen for composite preparation. The SEM images (Fig. 9 b-d) show that the processing temperature influences the inter-phase morphology of the composites. Partial inter-phase connection around the fibre is observed for the fabricated at 153 °C (Fig. 9 b). An increase in adhesion area is observed at the higher processing temperatures (Fig. 9 c-d).

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 9. SEM images of (a) Ingeo™ PLA fibre and PLA single composites processed at (b) 153 °C (c) 163 °C. and (d) 173 °C.

Table 3 Mechanical properties of Ingeo™ PLA fibre.

	Yield stress (MPa)	Stress at break (MPa)	Elongation (%)
Ingeo™ fibre	81.86 ± 5.40	81.24 ± 5.61	21.75 ± 5.63

Mechanical Properties and Structure of Annealed Fibre at Processing Temperature

Mechanical properties of the PLA fibre after annealing for 5 min at different temperatures are shown in Fig. 9. It was found that the tensile stress of annealed fibres at all temperatures was lower than the received (no heated) fibre (Table 3). The X-ray diffraction measurement shows a reduction intensity at $\sim 20^\circ$ ($Co, 2\theta$) indicating a crystalline disruption upon heating. This may be the reason for mechanical properties reduction in the composite that was prepared at temperature higher than the melting temperature of PLA fibre.

Figure 10 Mechanical property of PLA fibre after an annealing for 5 minutes at the processing temperature.

Figure 11 X-ray diffractograms of PLA fibre after an annealing for 5 minutes at the processing temperature.

CONCLUSION

Poly(lactic acid) based single composite has been prepared using a cast film extrusion technique. PLA matrix has been plasticized with triethyl O-acetyl citrate and reinforced by Ingeo™ PLA fibres. Effects of processing temperatures (153 °C, 163 °C and 173 °C), fibre contents (1.0, 3.0 and 5.0 % wt/wt) and fibre sizes (0.25, 1.0 and 3.0 mm) on the mechanical properties and morphology of the composites were investigated. Mechanical properties of the composite were declined upon the increase in processing temperature indicating a dramatic change of fibre shape and crystalline destruction. An increase in fibre content showed a small reduction of mechanical properties of the composites. This resulted from a poor dispersion and inter-phase adhesion in the composite with the selected processing temperature that was 153 °C. Better result was found in a processing temperature of 163 °C with similar fibre size and content. The 1.0 mm fibre length provided highest tensile strength at break compared to the other sizes of 0.25 and 3.0 mm.

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